

Smart Tourism Planning Framework for Sri Lanka: A Data-Driven Review and Conceptual System Model

P.M.W.B. Weerakoon¹, K.G.S.G. Kiriwalla^{2*}, M.G.A. Dinesh³

¹*Faculty of Information Technology, Horizon Campus, Malabe, Sri Lanka.*

Abstract

Sri Lanka hosts millions of tourists every year, but foreign visitors often struggle with inefficient trip planning, which is wasteful and reduces travel satisfaction. This literature review of existing scholarship identifies current knowledge on determinants of tourism planning and technological remedies to identify key knowledge gaps for Sri Lankan tourism growth. According to PRISMA principles, a search was performed in IEEE Xplore, ScienceDirect, Google Scholar, and tourism databases for peer-reviewed literature published between 2015-2023. From 156 preliminary sources, 29 studies that meet the inclusion criteria were selected. From the analysis of the studies, four general research topics emerged: environmental factors, including seasonality and weather; social factors, including crowd management and economic considerations, such as budget optimization; and technology solutions, including recommendation systems and mobile applications. The majority of research focuses on temperate Western targets and neglects tropical monsoon environments almost entirely. Current technology uses rarely integrate more than one group of planning variables simultaneously, and South Asian market cultural adjustment lacks empirical research to base the findings on. The review identifies three core gaps: absence of Sri Lanka-focused empirical studies examining planning determinants, deficiency of multi-factor integration methodologies, and lack of adequate cultural customization of the dominant tourism technology solutions. These findings form the foundation for destination-specific empirical research that can feed into evidence-based policy making and culturally grounded technology design for South Asia's emerging tourist destinations.

Keywords: *Tourism Planning Determinants, Systematic Review, Research Gaps, South Asian Tourism, Smart Tourism Technology.*